

ETHICS OF POWER MANIPULATION: A READING OF ACTS 8:9-24 IN THE CONTEXT OF AFRICAN CHRISTIANITY

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Ethics, Power Manipulation. Re-reading of Acts 8:9-24. Context, African Christianity.

Abstract: *This study engages in a Critical Critique of the manipulation of spiritual power in contemporary African Christianity by conducting a near-exegesis of the Simon Magus passage in Acts 8:9-24. Simon's account, who attempted to commercialize the apostolic gift of the Holy Spirit, offers a viable hermeneutical key for analyzing related phenomena in the African milieu. The study contends that the ethical failure indicated in Acts 8:9-24 is not one of Simon, but a fundamental misunderstanding of spiritual power in that it is looked at as misapprehension finds recurring resonance in present day African Christian contexts, especially within certain verity of Pentecostalism and charismatic circles, where spiritual power is sometimes capitalized on for financial gain, political control, and consolidation of personal dominance. Adopting a methodology of content- and context-based biblical hermeneutics, the investigation places the Acts text in critical dialogue with major African Christian praxis. The paper examines how the African worldview that upholds the reality of spiritual power might be employed by a "Simonistic" logic that tends to reduce the Holy Spirit to a negotiable commodity for earthly achievement. The study suggests that the Lukan ethical response and Peter's forceful rebuke and summons to repentance constitute a prophetic challenge to African Christianity. The paper recommends a transformative theological reflection and reorientation on power, distinguished by accountability and grace towards service rather than domination. By reading Acts 8:9-24 reflectively, the study recommends an authentic African Christian ethic that is both faithful to the Bible and contextually responsible to Africans as follows: 1. Integrate contextualized ethics into curricula. 2. Foster a theology of "power as service". 3. Re-emphasize the theology of the Holy Spirit. 4. Promote prophetic dialogue with the cultural reality of spiritual power while redirecting the human desire to control that power toward God.*

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Introduction

The account of Simon Magus in Acts 8:9-24 provides a critical biblical case on the unethical joining of spiritual power and material success. Simon, who “had previously practiced sorcery in the city and astonished the people of Samaria, claiming that he was someone. Great” Acts 8:9 NKJV) and who wanted to buy the apostolic authority to use the Holy Spirit served him a stern rebuke from Peter (Acts 8:20), personifies the ingrained temptation to commercialize divine power. The scenario here offers a contemporary parallel in circles of African Christianity, where the meeting of traditional worldviews, socio-economic pressures, and modern media advertisements has prompted similar practices. The challenge is the multiplication of what Clifford (2015) called the “prosperity gospel and its simulacra of power,” in which religious ascendancy is often used for material gain, reflecting Simon’s sin of Simony. This produces an ethical problem that erodes ecclesial integrity and exploits the faith of unsuspecting people (Karkkainen, 2021).

The study aims to conduct a critical exegetical analysis of Acts 8:9-24 to craft an engaging ethical framework for evaluating the dynamics of power and manipulation in African Christian landscapes. The work is not only descriptive but also offers a normative theological standard gleaned from the biblical text itself. The paper has some significance as follows: It responds to

an urgent and crucial pastoral concern by providing a scriptural mirror for critiquing manipulative praxes. It offers a broader academic engagement with African Pentecostalism, the Charismatic movement, and African independent or indigenous Churches, going deeper than sociological description to theological-ethical assessment and employing core biblical hermeneutics in its pursuit. In this manner, the study bridges a critical gap in African biblical hermeneutics by highlighting how the current text speaks prophetically to contemporary challenges. It brings into the academic space a positive theology of power for African Christianity grounded in Christocentric servanthood and the unmanageable sovereignty of the Holy Spirit. The study offers a resource for ecclesial Reform and Laity empowerment by developing ethical codes and providing tools for the laity to cultivate discernment. It also enriches the global conversation on world Christianity. It indicates how a non-Western context can offer fresh, critical, and biblical readings of scripture that challenge and strengthen global theological discourse.

This present study aims to fill the literature lacuna left by previous endeavours in the field. Mount (2015) indicates that the reception history of Simon Magus was purely Western in approach, leaving African application untouched. In the same manner, Spencer (2008) did not extend its ethical conclusions beyond the first century and did not show how this text aligns with or differs from non-Western

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Christian practices. Additionally, Clifford's (1998 & 2004) studies offer a broad critique of socio-economic and theological issues, but lack exegetical focus. Asamoah-Gyadu (2013) failed to use Simon Magus' narrative as a core biblical lens to argue for the dark side of the power theology he proposes.

Consequently, this study fills this obvious gap by proposing to engage the African reception history of Simon Magus that is devoid of the "Contextual Ethical exegesis" which Spencer failed to offer, to give the "Central Exegetical Anchor" that Clifford and Asamoah-Gyadu omit, and to apply the "Hermeneutical Method" of Adamo and Ukpong to the crucial, yet neglected text of Acts 8:9-24.

Literature Review

The literature review engages conceptual frameworks of power and manipulation, reviews three theoretical frameworks, examines empirical research on the African milieu, and identifies gaps this study intends to fill.

Conceptual Framework

Ethics in its broad sense refers to the systematic study of moral principles, the norms by which human actions are assessed right or wrong, good or bad. Similarly, in the Christian framework, ethics refers to how believers live in relation to God, the neighbour, and the created order, engaging scripture, tradition, and reason. In this instance, the Salvation Army posits that "Power, whether it is economic, emotional, legal, physical, political, psychological, religious or social, should always be exercised so as to

promote the values of the Kingdom of God, such as love, justice and mutual respect (The Salvation Army, 2011). Therefore, in this study, the ethical concern asks "how should power be and how the manipulation of power be assessed morally?"

The major concepts of this paper are "power" and its "manipulation" understood through the biblical narrative of Simon Magus in Acts 8:9-24. The idea of power is multifaceted. It refers to the capacity or ability to act, to influence or control, to change events or persons (Unger's 1996). In the view of Mkkize (2024), "Power is the ability to influence behaviour, to change the course of events, to overcome resistance, and to get people to do things they would not otherwise do." Power is also the ability to act effectively. It is a force that may be used for doing work (The Complete Christian Dictionary for Home and School, 1992). Power again refers to ability, strength, and absolute authority (Unger's 1966). In this dimension, power in Acts, referred to as (*dunamis*), is a manifestation of the Holy Spirit that confirms the gospel message and develops the group of believers (Spencer, 2008). The experience with Simon Magus presents an interpretive challenge. Simon, a practitioner of magic (*Mageia*), signifies a worldview in which spiritual power is a neutral force that may be obtained, operated, and engaged by the expert in the field.

In the words of Spencer (2008), Simon felt that the apostolic power was a higher-grade magic that ought to be purchased by a financial transaction. This sharply disagrees with Luke's

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perspective on the Holy Spirit as a Sovereign divine Person, given only by God (Acts 8:20). The ethical inappropriateness does not lie only in monetary greed but also in a basic misunderstanding of the essence of spiritual power: a divine gift rather than commodification.

Manipulation denotes the control or influence of another person's emotions, thoughts or actions by covert, deceptive or exploitative means. In a philosophical sense, manipulation is defined as "Steering or influencing the choices of others by what might be morally problematic (though not necessarily wrong in all cases (Wood, 2014). The author further explains the three forms of manipulation: deception, pressure, and exploitation of emotional vulnerability or character defects (Wood, 2014). A detailed explanation holds that manipulation occurs when the inspirer intends to affect the target (agency + intention) and uses methods that circumvent rational thinking or exploit vulnerabilities, thereby undermining autonomy (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy Archive, 2020). Manipulation differs from rational persuasion because it influences behaviour by means that do not engage the target's thought process (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy Archive, 2020).

In this sense, Simon Magus employed sorcery to manipulate the people of Samaria in Acts 8:9-11. This is certain because sorcery is the practice of engaging supernatural powers or magic, often with the aid of evil spirits, to influence or inspire

events or to manipulate people. The term is frequently associated with witchcraft, divination, and the occult (Bible Hub, 2025).

Re-reading is another word in the title that needs to be unpacked. The re-reading of biblical text is a critical aspect of modern hermeneutics, particularly in Africa and Asia, where the Bible functions as a theological and socio-ethical resource (Ukpong, 1995; West & Dube, 2000). The word re-reading refers to the interpretive act employing a biblical passage afresh, sometimes from viewpoints overlooked by theological traditions. From a Re-reading standpoint, meaning is not exhausted by historical-critical investigation but persists as the text interacts with contemporary experiences (Thiselton, 2009). In this manner, re-reading in biblical hermeneutics indicates a dialogue between the ancient text and the modern reader, offering a reinterpretation that bridges historical intention and contemporary significance (West, 2019). Re-reading, which entails "second reading" (Ukpong, 2000), posits that every re-reading ought to address the socio-political realities that fashion both the reader and the interpretive milieu (Dube, 2000).

In this way, re-reading tends to recover certain aspects of meaning repressed by traditional or colonial readings (Dube, 2000). It contextualizes biblical ethics, making them relevant to modern moral situations, thereby offering transformative purposes that connect the biblical text with the realities of life (Ukpong, 2000; West, 2019). It enables local people to

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interpret the biblical text through their own experiences, thereby democratizing the process of biblical interpretation (Mosala, 1989). In the present study, re-reading operates as the conceptual lens by which the ethics of power manipulation are examined. This framework combines the biblical text (Acts 8:9-28), the hermeneutical model (contextual and postcolonial re-reading), and the African socio-ethical context to offer new insights into the biblical text.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical frameworks for this study are Rudolf Otto's theory of the numinous, the phenomenological theory of religion, and the African theological ethical framework. Combined, they offer a hermeneutical and moral window for re-reading Acts 8:9-24 in the context of African Christianity, intersected by power, authority, and exploitation. In this regard, Rudolf Otto's (1958) theory of the numinous provides an essential phenomenological interpretation of religion as an encounter with "the *mysterium tremendum et fascinans*," the holy that simultaneously evokes awe, fear, and attraction. For Otto, the nature of religion is in the human response to divine otherness, which is an import that is irrational and morally "re-engineering." In Acts 8:9-24, Simon Magus's intention to purchase the Holy Spirit signals a distortion of the text's encounter: Simon was drawn by the *fascinans* (attraction to divine power), but lacked the *tremendum* (reverential awe) necessary to appreciate the

manifestation. Consequently, in contemporary African Christianity, Otto's window aids the examination of the same tendencies in modern Churches, where divine power is commodified or exploited for pride and aggrandizement (Otto, 2006; Sharpe, 1986).

Phenomenological Theory of Religion

This is coined by Edmund Husserl (1913) and fleshed by Gerardus Van der Leeuw (1933), which helps the study to interpret religious realities as they manifest to the mind of the Christian. By engaging the *epoche* - the suspension of judgment, phenomenology grants the scripture to speak within its lived spiritual context. This interpretive viewpoint sheds light on how the early believers experienced divine power as a gift rather than a possession. It also indicated Simon's attitude as a misconception of religious encounter, in which he viewed divine power as transferable and purchasable rather than a sacred endowment through God's grace. In the African context, the phenomenological happening from exploitative or manipulative religious activities that diminish the difference between spirituality and show (Smart, 1973).

African Theological-Ethical Framework

This particular framework locates the study in the African moral and social worldview. African scholars such as Bediako (2004), Kalu (2009), and Muigambi (2009) stress that Christian ethics in Africa should uphold Ubuntu, a moral vision rooted in communality, integrity, and service. Simon's attempt to misuse divine power

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disrupted this communal life and diminished the ethical essence of leadership in the African Church. The African view of biblical teaching offers a moral corrective: that divine endowment is not for personal pride and gain but for communal transformation of the Church and wider society. This framework aligns with Peter's corrective stance, confirming that spiritual gifts must be exercised under divine guidance and with ethical accountability. Integrating these frameworks offers an interpretive matrix for re-reading Acts 8:9-24 as an enduring ethical lens on power manipulation, both then and now in the early Church.

Methodology

This paper adopts a qualitative interpretive methodology rooted in content and African semiotic analysis, combined with intercultural hermeneutics. These procedures are used to unpack the ethical and didactic meanings in Acts 8:9-24, especially in relation to African Christian experiences of power and spirituality.

Content analysis gives the first interpretive tool. Through content analysis, the study finds recurring motifs of power, manipulation, and spiritual authenticity. In this regard, Mayring (2021) remarks that qualitative content analysis provides a structured yet malleable method of interpreting scriptural data through unpacking untapped meaning within the account and discourse. This approach throws light on the ethical tension between divine empowerment and human desires, which is central to the Simon

story. In addition to the above method, African semiotics analysis interprets biblical symbols through an African cultural lens. Semiotics examines how meanings are constructed using signs and cultural codes. Providing further insight, Danesi (2020) argues that Semiotics is essential for reading Acts 8:9-24 within the symbolic setting of African religiosity, where charisma, spiritual power, and prosperity often converge. In this perspective, Simon Magus' ambition to "buy" the power of the Holy Spirit parallels some African charismatic urge to commercialize divine gifts, serving a content-sensitive evaluation of spiritual manipulation (Adekambi, 2023). In the African milieu, power is a symbol of pride, authority and influence. Simon Magus wanted greater power from Peter so he could feel more pride, gain greater authority, and control people.

The study is strengthened further by engaging intercultural hermeneutics, which reconciles the ancient biblical world with modern African content. This procedure, advocated by African scholars such as Ukpogon (2001, 2002) and reaffirmed by Mojola (2022), stresses a dialogical encounter between text and reader, in which African socio-religious realities inform and are transformed by the scriptural message. Intercultural hermeneutics recognizes that biblical meaning is not static but emerges from the interaction of communities of believers across time, space, and culture (Uzukwu, 2015). In this way, the study situates Simon's moral failure within African Christianity's

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contemporary struggle with syncretism, ministerial pride, and clerical influence. The integration of these methodologies produces a multifaceted depth of interpretation. In consequence, uncovers the ethical aspects of power manipulation in Acts 8 and, pivotally, aligns with African ecclesial realities where divine power is sometimes commodified and/or commercialized.

Exegesis Proper

The exegesis proper will take the following pathways: Literary context, historical-cultural setting, citing the text in transliterated Greek and English, and grammatical analysis of key words in the passage.

Literary context of Acts 8:9-24

The locating of Simon Magus' account within the structure of the Acts of the Apostles is crucially thematically arranged. It serves as a transaction point and a theological case study. In the immediate context (Acts 8:1-8, 14-25): The text is located immediately after the killing of Stephen and the break-out of serious persecution against the Church in Jerusalem (Acts 8:1b). This persecution resulted in believers "scattering throughout the regions of Judea and Samaria" (Acts 8:1c). Philip, one of the seven chosen in Acts 6:5, goes to Samaria and preaches, performing signs and wonder and drawing large following (Acts 8:5-8). This is the direct fulfillment of the geographical and ethical intentions of Luke in Acts 1:8. "You will be my witnesses in Jerusalem, in all Judea and Samaria, and to the ends of the earth." The

Samaria mission outside the Jewish world is what Thompson (2011, p. 135) calls "the first of a series of landmark breakthroughs" in the Lukan account.

The wider context of Acts as a whole establishes a pattern and addresses a core theological concern: the confirmation of apostolic authority and the proper medium of the Holy Spirit. The necessity for Peter and John to arrive from Jerusalem to mediate the spirit (8:14-17) underscores that the mission to the New people is confirmed and merged under the authority of the Jerusalem apostles (Fitzmyer, 1998).

In the words of Keener (2013, p. 1503), the "apostolic authentication ensures the unity of the expanding church across ethnic lines." The narrative creates a contrast between true and false power, between the power of God and the power of human sorcery. Another reference to a similar theme is the confrontation between Paul and Elymas the magician on Cyprus (Acts 13:6-12).

The Lukan text of Acts 8 is important for another reason, which is the Simon Magus' Tradition." That formed the early Christian tradition, which became the archetypal heresiarch. The seed of Simony was planted in the story of Acts 8. In this manner, Luke shows Simon as the first main internal threat to the purity of the gospel message, the threat of Simony, which is the buying and selling of spiritual power rather than external persecution (Brower, 2019, p. 42). The insertion of a chiasm in Peter's rebuke in Acts 8:20-23 is a literary structure that reveals the

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central sin of Simony (Barrett, 1994). The rhetorical import highlights a sharp distinction between the apostolic gospel of grace and Simon's view, grounded in possession or commodification (Marshall, 2020, p. 88).

Historical-Cultural Setting - offers the key to understanding the historical-cultural environment in which the confrontation in the text happened. This is a Samaritan-Jewish background that is crucial in that Jews and Samaritans were severely divided. To the Jewish mind, the idea that the Samaritans accepted the gospel was incredible. Philip's achievement and the apostles' confirmation mean the breaking down of ethnic barriers to the flow of the gospel. The world of the Greco-Roman Magic fertilized magical display. Magicians and "Divine men" called magoi were common vendors of spiritual power. Simon's acclamation from the entertained crowd, "to whom they all gave heed, from the least to the greatest, saying, "This man is the great power of God" Acts 8:10), reveals the common scene in the milieu. Modern scholars of magical practices remark that such persons were not taken as frauds but as powerful mediators of supernatural knowledge, suggesting that Simon's dispute with the apostles was an encounter between opposing systems of power (Klutz, 2008). In this context, Magic was a profitable profession, and spiritual power was a skill to be acquired and a salable commodity. Therefore, Peter's reaction was a revolutionary rejection of the culturally acceptable worldview.

In the same vein, there existed the patronage system and benefaction; in that sense, Simon's offer of money highlights an effort to start a patron-client relationship, which would have introduced buying into the apostles' circle of power. Peter's rebuke challenges the understanding, setting a new paradigm that the gift of God is not a commodity for a patronage network. Furthermore, the laying on of hands was a sign of apostolic authority and divine blessing (Fitzmyer, 1998, p. 407). The spirit falling after the apostles' arrival and the laying on of hands is consistent with Luke's account elsewhere in Acts 9:17; 13:2, 3, signifying healing and authorization, as the case may be.

The account of Simon Magus in Acts 8:9-24 is a powerfully composed history. Literally, it provides an essential validation of the Samaritan mission, confirms apostolic authority and establishes a classic internal threat to the Church. Historically, it greatly reveals the core of Samaritan-Jewish tensions, the prevalent culture of Greco-Roman magic, and the socio-economic structures of patronage-client relations.

Eventually, reading the passage through these double lenses, we glean that the conflict is not just the fall of Simon Magus, the notable magician, but a fundamental clash between the economy of divine grace and the economy of human power and mechanization. This is the literary and historical setting of Acts 8:9-24.

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Citing Acts 8:9-24 in Greek and English.

Acts 8:9–24 — Greek Transliteration

9

Anēr de tis onomati Simōn proypērchen en tē polei mageuōn kai existanōn to ethnos tēs Samareias, legōn einai tina heauton megan.

10

Hō proseichon pantes apo mikrou heōs megalou, legontes, Houtos estin hē dynamis tou Theou hē kaloumenē Megalē.

11

Proseichon de autō dia to hikanō chronō existakenai autous tais mageiais.

12

Hote de episteusan tō Philippo euangelizomenō peri tēs basileias tou Theou kai tou onomatos Iēsou Christou, ebaptizonto andres te kai gynaikes.

13

Ho de Simōn kai autos episteusen, kai baptistheis ēn proskarterōn tō Philippo, theōrōn te sēmeia kai dynameis megalas ginomenas existato.

14

Akousantes de hoi en Ierusalēm apostoloi hoti dedektai hē Samareia ton logon tou Theou, apesteilan pros autous Petron kai Iōannēn,

15

hoitines katabantes prosēuxanto peri autōn hopōs labōsin Pneuma Hagion.

16

Oudepō gar ēn ep' oudeni autōn epipeptōkos, monon de bebaptismenoi hyparchon eis to onoma tou Kyriou Iēsou.

17

Tote epetithesan tas cheiras ep' autous, kai elambanon Pneuma Hagion.

18

Idōn de ho Simōn hoti dia tēs epitheseōs tōn cheirōn tōn apostolōn didotai to Pneuma, prosēnenken autois chrēmata,

19

legōn, Dote kamoī tēn exousian tautēn, hina hō ean epithō tas cheiras lambanē Pneuma Hagion.

20

Petros de eipen pros auton, To argyrion sou syn soi eiē eis apōleian, hoti tēn dōrean tou Theou enomisas dia chrēmatōn ktasthai.

21

Ouk estin soi meris oude klēros en tō logō toutō, hē gar kardia sou ouk estin eutheia enanti tou Theou.

22

Metanoēson oun apo tēs kakias sou tautēs kai deēthēti tou Kyriou, ei ara aphethēsetai soi hē epinoia tēs kardias sou.

23

Eis gar cholēn pikrias kai syndesmon adikias horō se onta.

24

Apokritheis de ho Simōn eipen, Deēthēte hymeis hyper emou pros ton Kyrion, hopōs mēden epepelthē ep' eme hōn eirēkate.

Acts 8:9–24 — American Standard Version (1901)

9 But there was a certain man, Simon by name, who before time in the city used sorcery, and amazed the people of Samaria, giving out that he

Rev'd Anyanwu, Charles Anozie, Phd and Kokey, Grace Chinedum, Phd

was some great one:

10 to whom they all gave heed, from the least to the greatest, saying, This man is that power of God which is called Great.

11 And they gave heed to him, because for a long time he had amazed them with his sorceries.

12 But when they believed Philip preaching good tidings concerning the kingdom of God and the name of Jesus Christ, they were baptized, both men and women.

13 And Simon also himself believed: and being baptized, he continued with Philip; and beholding signs and great miracles wrought, he was amazed.

14 Now when the apostles who were at Jerusalem heard that Samaria had received the word of God, they sent Peter and John.

15 who, when they came down, prayed for them, that they might receive the Holy Spirit:

16 for as yet it had fallen upon none of them: only they had been baptized into the name of the Lord Jesus.

17 Then laid them their hands on them, and they received the Holy Spirit.

18 Now, when Simon saw that through the laying on of the apostles' hands the Holy Spirit was given, he offered them money,

19 saying, Give me also this power, that on whomsoever I lay my hands, he may receive the Holy Spirit.

20 But Peter said unto him, Thy silver perish with thee, because thou hast thought to obtain the gift of God with money.

21 Thou hast neither part nor lot in this matter:

for thy heart is not right before God.

22 Repent therefore of this thy wickedness, and pray the Lord, if perhaps the thought of thy heart shall be forgiven thee.

23 For I see that thou art in the gall of bitterness and in the bond of iniquity.

24 And Simon answered and said, Pray ye for me to the Lord, that none of the things which ye have spoken come upon me.

Exegesis Proper

Acts 8:9-24 offers a profound exploration of the ethical use of power within the early church. This passage contrasts Simon the magician, who seeks personal advancement through spiritual influence, with Philip, whose ministry is characterized by service and integrity under divine guidance. By integrating the Greek text, this exegesis reveals the subtleties of language that highlight the ethical dimensions of leadership, influence, and spiritual authority, providing insight for contemporary Christian communities.

1. Simon's Seductive Spell: Power as Personal Possession (Acts 8:9-11)

The narrative begins with Simon, described as the power of God that is called great ἄνθρωπος δὲ τις ὀνόματι Σίμων, προϊὼν ἐν τῇ πόλει, θαυματοποιός, ἐδίδασκεν τὸν λαὸν καὶ ἐθαύμαζον πάντες (Acts 8:9-10). The Greek verb ἐδίδασκεν indicates that Simon actively taught and influenced the people, while θαυματοποιός emphasizes the wonder-inducing nature of his acts, attracting admiration and loyalty. However, Simon's motivation is

Rev'd Anyanwu, Charles Anozie, Phd and Kokey, Grace Chinedum, Phd

rooted in self-interest, as later revealed when he attempts to purchase the power of the Holy Spirit (v.18: ἰδὼν ὅτι διὰ τῆς χειρὸς τῶν ἀποστόλων δίδεται τὸ πνεῦμα ἅγιον). Ethically, this demonstrates the dangers of exploiting spiritual gifts for personal gain, of prioritizing showmanship over service, and of manipulating communal trust (Hengel, 1974; Marshall, 1980). Simon's example serves as a cautionary tale of charisma unmoored from accountability, where impressive displays can mask moral corruption.

2. Apostolic model: Power as Proclamatory catalyst Affirmation (Acts 8:12-13)

The apostles exercise spiritual authority ethically through the laying on of hands (ἐπέθηκαν τὰς χεῖρας). The Greek verb ἐπέθηκαν conveys both blessing and commissioning, signifying divinely guided transfer of spiritual power. Opposite what Simon did, the apostles demonstrate that influence must align with divine purpose, operate under communal oversight, and maintain integrity in its execution (Keener, 2012). This action demonstrates the necessity of accountability in leadership, ensuring that power serves the community and respects divine mandates. The passage highlights that ethical leadership is not only about authority but also about responsibility and stewardship. The power of God must be used to serve the Church and humanity, not for self-glorification. The result of power used properly is belief and baptism, even as Simon himself believed and was baptized and not just for entertainment.

Rev'd Anyanwu, Charles Anozie, Phd and Kokey, Grace Chinedum, Phd

3. Decisive Confrontation: Gift versus Commodity

Simon's misguided request, δότε μοι καὶ ἐμοὶ τὴν ἐξουσίαν ταύτην, illustrates his attempt to commodify spiritual gifts. The Greek ἐξουσία emphasizes dominion and control rather than service, highlighting the ethical breach in his approach. Peter's rebuke, μισθὸν γὰρ τὸ πρᾶγμα ὑμῶν (v.20), signifies the moral principle that spiritual authority cannot be merchandised or exploited. This passage ethically instructs leaders and communities on the responsible exercise of spiritual power, showing that misuse undermines trust, distorts ministry, and harms the community's spiritual well-being (Wright, 2008). It reveals that power devoid of moral application leads to subversion and corruption. African Church leaders must confront hints of magic or misuse of spiritual powers and spiritual gifts in the Church and elsewhere. Any sign of abuse or exploitations of spiritual gifts must be sharply rebuked as Peter did to Simon Magus "May your silver perish with you, because you thought you could buy the gift of God with money (Acts 8:20). The Christians' need for spiritual power or gift must be out of pure heart to engage it in the service of God and man.

4. Philip's Ethical Practice of Power

Philip demonstrates ethical exercise of power through teaching (ἐκήρυξεν αὐτοῖς τὸν Χριστόν) and facilitating voluntary commitment to the gospel. The Greek verbs ἐπίστευσαν and ἐβαπτίσθησαν signify informed belief and responsible reception of faith. His guidance of

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the Ethiopian eunuch (v. 26: ἄγγελος δὲ κυρίου ἐλάλησεν τῷ Φίλιππῳ) shows ethical leadership that respects autonomy, promotes understanding, and enables transformative lives. Philip's example reveals that influence modelled in service, integrity, and respect for choice results in sustainable spiritual growth and community edification (Polhill, 1992). Philip's pedagogy posits that the pure power of God should be instructive, directional towards God and His kingdom, and not to man.

Context of African Christianity

The African variety of Christianity is diverse, dynamic, and continually growing within the Christian faith worldwide. It is distinguished by integration of biblical revelation with indigenous cultural, social, and religious realities (Bediako, 2004; Sannech, 2009). Within this complex context, inquiries into power, authority, and ethics take on special meanings that shape both belief and praxis. Christianity in Africa grows within societies where religion pervades all areas of life, namely, social, economic, political and spiritual (Mbiti, 1999). In this type of setting, power is viewed as a spiritual force that boosts life, safeguards the community and aids cosmological balance.

Spiritual Power and Leadership

In African Christianity, spiritual power is often equated with divine authorization for ministry, prophecy, healing, and deliverance, which might lead to competition among practitioners. It has been noted by Kalu (2008) that "Charismatic power has become a major symbol of legitimacy

among African Pentecostal (p. 34). The quest for like legitimacy can sometimes obscure ethical limits, leading to manipulative behaviour.

The account of Simon the sorcerer in Acts 8:9-24 captures this kind of tension. Like Simon Magus, who sought to buy spiritual authority or power, some modern African religious practitioners commercialize spiritual gifts for personal aggrandizement, rendering divine power into a business commodity (Ukah, 2020).

Cultural Conceptions of Power and Authority

Africans have valued communal order and respect for authority since ancient times. In recent times, encounters between Christianity and traditional power structures have often led to syncretic distortions, in which leaders become autocratic or resort to magical means to control citizens opposed to Christ's servant-leadership model (Katongole, 2017). Acts 8:9-24 serves as a good example of ethical critique of such distortions, warning African Christians that spiritual authority is a gift of God's grace, not a transaction item for sale or control.

Ethical Re-orientation in African Christianity

As a result of what has been above, African Christianity faces a challenge to re-explain the ethics of power within the framework of Biblical Servanthood and community transformation. In this sense, Bediako (2024) argues that the renewal of African Christianity ought to emerge from culture but be guided by the ethical standards of scripture.

Rev'd Anyanwu, Charles Anozie, Phd and Kokey, Grace Chinedum, Phd

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Conclusion

Acts 8:9-27 presents a compelling contrast between misused and ethically stewarded power. Simon's manipulation represents self-interest and exploitation, while Philip's ministry embodies integrity, transparency, and communal accountability. The Greek text emphasizes voluntary belief (*ἐπίστευσαν*) and the responsible transfer of authority (*ἐπέθηκον*), highlighting that ethical power respects autonomy, promotes informed engagement, and supports communal trust. African Church leaders are called to exercise authority as servant-leaders rather than dominating others by scheming, ensuring that their influence contributes positively to both spiritual and communal well-being of the people. This passage underscores the ethical responsibilities inherent in positions of influence. Simon's approach warns against self-serving manipulation, whereas Philip and the

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apostles exemplify power exercised with ethical integrity, transparency, and service to the community. Ethical leadership, therefore, is characterized by alignment with divine purpose, respect for autonomy, and accountability within the community.

Recommendations

The study emphasizes ethical leadership training that should cultivate a service-oriented understanding of power.

There should be accountability structures in Churches to maintain transparent systems to prevent abuse.

Church Communities should promote informed engagement and encourage believers to make voluntary, informed spiritual commitments.

Leadership practices should be regularly evaluated to ensure alignment with biblical and moral standards.

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Rev'd Anyanwu, Charles Anozie, Phd and Kokey, Grace Chinedum, Phd